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“THE MAN IN THE MIRROR”

The road did seem so dim and drear,
No soul desired to wander near,
Till I beheld a man alone,
Who lived for self, with naught his own.

I gazed within his weary eyes,
And found therein our common sighs;
In him I found another me,
A soul bereft of joy and glee.

Though lonely was his mournful state,
I spake in jest to soften fate;
Yet naught that I could speak or do
Could cleanse the grief he suffered through.

No word of mine could ease his pain,
Nor dry the tears that fell like rain.
Most blessed was I his company to see,
Like unto a shadow that ne'er would flee.

In darkest hours I left him not,
Together bound in light forgot;
And oft when he to ruin fell,
I saw him strive and bear it well.

He was the kind who wept with thee,
And smiled when joy thy heart did see.
Yet once, the man I saw no more—
I sought for him on every shore.

A thousand miles he went away,
Yet still I prayed he'd come and stay,
If but awhile he might return,

Whilst still within my heart did yearn.

I waited long, yet none came back;
That night was drowned in utter black.
I lit a candle in my room,
Whilst thunder spake of coming doom.

Then toward the mirror cast mine eye,
And saw the man once more thereby.
Yet changed was he from what I knew,
And wiser far from all he'd been through.

